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Pandemic Prevention Paradigms: Understanding Global Health Governance

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ABSTRACT

One Health is an emerging area of integrative studies and interventions aimed at preventing zoonotic diseases by addressing human, animal, and environmental interactions. A fundamental aspect of the concept is understanding how these interactions influence health outcomes among humans, animals, and ecosystems. Developed initially to respond to the need for more human and veterinary medicine collaboration, One Health must include social and environmental dimensions and biomedicine to establish a biomedical-integrative system. A comprehensive approach must also be applied to the research's social, biological, historical, and local aspects. With One Health, health-related disciplines can be reconciled, and its transdisciplinary imperative will provide solutions to the limitations of current biomedical and public health principles. This article aims to discuss and define zoonoses in different sectors. Accordingly, it calls for developing an international priority-setting framework to monitor, report, and assess zoonoses following their relative health conditions in epidemic, endemic, and pandemic settings. Current models of global health governance in pandemic prevention still face challenges, such as policy incoherence, response delays, and inequity in resource access. International coordination, investment in surveillance systems, and promotion of information transparency are key strategies for improving health crisis management. Accordingly, it is suggested that member states of international organizations participate more actively in establishing cooperation frameworks and develop more effective implementation mechanisms for managing emerging health threats. To safeguard global health security, policymakers, researchers, and public health officials will find insights, recommendations, and actionable strategies in this article.

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1 | Introduction

A pandemic is a large-scale outbreak of an infectious disease that causes significant morbidity and mortality across a broad geographical area, disrupting the economy, society, and political systems [1–3]. Human history has witnessed several significant pandemics that negatively impact health, economies, and national security [4, 5]. Globally, governments, United Nations agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and donors from various sectors, such as livestock, public health, and health-care, are increasingly interested in One Health and the spread of zoonotic diseases [6, 7]. Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is just the latest example of a series of pandemics that threatened humans.

One Health is an integrated, multisectoral approach that considers the links between human, animal, and environmental health and emphasizes interdisciplinary collaboration for disease prevention and control [8, 9]. Zoonotic diseases are infections transmitted from animals to humans and can be caused by viruses, bacteria, parasites, or fungi [10, 11]. Zoonotic diseases, such as COVID-19 and Crimean–Congo fever, have a significant public health impact and require comprehensive approaches to control and prevent them. One Health is inherently interdisciplinary, with its fundamental goal of extending research and interventions from clinics and laboratories to local communities, particularly in agricultural landscapes and natural ecosystems [12, 13]. Understanding diseases from a medical perspective, including their causes, pathogenesis, management, and how infections develop, spread, are controlled, eradicated, or eliminated [10, 14, 15]. This approach involves conventional public health practices and social and environmental factors, promoting inclusivity and collaboration across diverse fields.

The emergence of novel zoonotic diseases caused by emerging pathogens requires the converging incorporation of human and veterinary medicine through public health [16, 17]. It is also imperative to fight the re-emergence the persistence of endemic zoonotic illnesses, particularly neglected tropical diseases [18, 19]. One Health has, therefore, gained much attention since its conception. A proactive approach to preventing pandemics and mitigating associated health concerns and local epidemics and outbreaks is increasingly cited as an essential part of the solution [20, 21]. Traditional medical practices, epidemiology, and public health, including human and veterinary care, cannot deal with this global health challenge, which should be addressed by developing new knowledge, skills, and strategies [22–24]. Furthermore, the environmental dimension helps bridge the gap among these disciplines. Environmental changes can influence pathogen–vector–host interactions, making it challenging to predict endemic, epidemic, and zoonotic diseases in complex ways [25–28].

Due to the lack of a holistic approach to combat zoonoses, One Health has been challenging to implement in recent decades [29, 30]. An emerging approach to environmental management uses ecosystems and adaptive management, such as forest management, wildlife management, fisheries management, and watershed management. The science of human–environmental systems has evolved to improve our understanding and outcomes of interventions [31, 32]. Recognizing that social and institutional

changes occur in patterns over time due to environmental factors, including those related to natural or ecological subsystems, is essential to this process [33]. Implementing scientific and practical initiatives to prevent outbreaks, epidemics, and pandemics of zoonotic conditions, One Health and other approaches aim to integrate academically and professionally diverse fields into a comprehensive health science for humans, animals, and ecosystems [34–37].

Despite progress, current global health governance frameworks continue to suffer from structural and functional weaknesses in the face of large-scale health crises such as pandemics [38]. The lack of coordination of policymaking among countries, delays in preventive measures, lack of transparency in information exchange, and inequality in access to health resources are among the most important obstacles to the effective prevention and control of pandemics [39, 40]. In addition, improving international cooperation, increasing investment in epidemiological research, and developing global standard protocols to deal with emerging threats can play a fundamental role in reducing the vulnerability of health systems.

Understanding how humans interact with their environments and function optimally in a healthy state is crucial [41, 42]. This knowledge is essential for effectively addressing One Health and emerging zoonoses [43]. It is imperative to take a broader view of health and integrate knowledge, methods, and skills from various disciplines and professions [44–46]. Understanding human–environment interactions is significant and necessary for comprehensively managing health issues. Infectious diseases that evolve into zoonoses and their global health consequences differ from other contagious diseases [47, 48]. In addition, it is imperative to investigate the processes and reasons behind how evolving zoonoses can trigger an epidemic or pandemic, the reasons for the re-emergence of previously controlled diseases, and the persistence of the old diseases [49–51]. This review article provides a comprehensive overview of the evolving landscape of pandemic prevention paradigms by combining case studies, success stories, challenges, and future directions. To safeguard global health security, policymakers, researchers, and public health officials will find insights, recommendations, and actionable strategies in this article (Figure 1).

2 | Search Strategy

This review conducted a comprehensive and systematic search in reputable scientific databases, including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, EMBASE, and ProQuest, to examine global health governance frameworks for pandemic prevention from 2015 to 2024. The search aimed to identify studies related to global policies for pandemic control and to examine the role of international organizations, intergovernmental collaborations, and national and regional strategies for reducing the threats posed by emerging and re-emerging diseases. Studies published in recent years up to the time of writing were reviewed to analyze the latest findings and policy approaches in the field of pandemic control and prevention. A combination of broad and relevant keywords was used to ensure comprehensive coverage of the sources.

FIGURE 1 | This conceptual model puts a pandemic prevention model with a proactive orientation at its heart, supported by several interrelated and complementary components. These key components include proactive early warning mechanisms. a, b, c) international collaboration, and worldwide governance for early awareness and timely reaction. d) Transparency and accountability are key underpinnings for adequate health security. E, f, g, h, i) It prioritizes rapid reaction mechanisms, equitable access to health assets, durable health infrastructure, and investments in development and investigation. The shield’s background connotes protection and represents a strengthened and consolidated reaction in safeguarding worldwide health.

These keywords comprised “global health governance,” “pandemic preparedness,” “One Health approach,” “zoonotic disease control,” “international health regulations,” “public health response,” “emerging infectious diseases,” “epidemic containment,” “health security frameworks,” “vaccine distribution policies,” “antimicrobial resistance,” “cross-border health threats,” “risk communication in pandemics,” “biosurveillance strategies,” “intergovernmental collaborations in public health,” “non-pharmaceutical interventions,” “disease outbreak response mechanisms,” “biodefense policies,” “health system resilience,” “public-private partnerships in disease control,” and “pandemic risk assessment models.” These keywords were searched in the

studies’ title, abstract, and keyword sections to identify all studies related to different dimensions of global health governance. After the initial search and retrieval of studies, the selected studies were screened on the basis of specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria included studies that examined macro and international policies in the area of global health governance and the role of international organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO), the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), the World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH), and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). Studies that discussed the One Health approach, the impact

of climate change on the spread of zoonotic diseases, global vaccination programs, the challenges of coordination among countries in managing pandemics, the economic and social effects of disease control policies, and the impact of worldwide trade and international travel on the transmission of pathogens were also included in this study.

In contrast, exclusion criteria included studies that focused solely on clinical aspects of diseases and studies limited to a specific country or region without relevance to international policies, limited case studies that lacked global generalizability, and studies that lacked policy analysis or sufficient data to examine global health governance frameworks. Studies published before the period of interest and lacking updates relevant to recent global policies were also excluded.

Finally, 240 studies were examined through qualitative content analysis to identify key trends, key challenges, and suggested solutions for improving global health governance frameworks. To increase the accuracy of the analysis, the selected articles were assessed in terms of various aspects such as methodological validity, citation rate, geographical coverage, impact on international policy, and relevance to the article's main topic.

3 | Zoonotic Disease Understanding

There are more than a billion cases and millions of fatalities annually due to zoonotic diseases [52, 53]. Most emerging infectious diseases (EIDs) and most recent pandemics are sparked by animals, mostly wildlife, and their development is often driven by dynamic interactions among wildlife, livestock, and people in rapidly changing environments [54, 55]. Agricultural interventions are available for most top-ranking zoonoses when they affect livestock, have a wildlife interface, and adversely impact livestock [56]. Diseases, such as gastrointestinal zoonoses, rabies, leptospirosis, anthrax, leishmaniasis, hydatid disease, Q fever, toxoplasmosis, and trypanosomiasis, have important reservoirs among wild animals nationwide [57–59]. In some cases, wildlife plays a crucial role in epidemiological circumstances. For instance, a few wildlife species from Tanzania and South Africa's national parks are at risk from tuberculosis, common among buffaloes, as well as hepatitis E and cysticercosis, which are prevalent among wild pigs [60].

Zoonoses are much harder to control where there is a wildlife interface. Other zoonoses with notable wildlife interfaces include Chagas disease, chikungunya, and Ebola; there are also psittacosis, avian influenza, and Rift Valley Fever [61]. As an example of zoonotic disease emergence from wildlife reservoirs, influenza viruses can be taken as an example [62, 63]. There are seasonal epidemic zoonoses brought about by influenza viruses and pandemic zoonoses, among the most morbid and fatal zoonoses [64, 65]. The episodic nature of their infections is caused by recurring animal–human virus transmission.

Many transmissible zoonoses, including influenza viruses, are responsible for seasonal flu outbreaks and most recent pandemics. These include the 1918 Spanish Flu, the Asian Flu in 1957, the Hong Kong Flu in 1968, the highly pathogenic avian influenza subtype H5N1 in 2003, and the 2009 Swine Flu [66–69].

Over 50–100 million people were killed by the most devastating pandemic of the 20th century, the Spanish Flu [70, 71]. In contrast, H5N1 caused a much smaller number of fatalities in humans, although it caused a large number of poultry deaths [72–74]. There are about 30 countries where this disease circulates as an endemic zoonosis, periodically leading to outbreaks of the disease in both domestic and wild birds [75, 76]. Moreover, it is possible to acquire it through human-to-human transmission through genetic reassortment [77, 78]. In the 2009 swine flu pandemic, fewer than a million people died, making it regarded as relatively mild [79].

A high transmission rate of respiratory diseases with avian origins broke the historical pattern of pandemics during the severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and COVID-19 pandemics [80–82]. In this context, vector-borne diseases (VBDs) pose significant challenges to human and veterinary health, representing a growing public health concern requiring effective surveillance and control strategies [83]. The incidence of these diseases in new regions has been growing due to various factors such as vector interactions, animal hosts, and climate conditions, all of which favor their global spread. Mosquitoes are primarily considered vectors for dengue, chikungunya, yellow fever, Zika, malaria, and Japanese encephalitis. Other vectors, including fleas, sandflies, mites, ticks, and lice, can also transmit these diseases. The co-infection of the coronavirus of a Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS-CoV-2) and VBDs has been estimated at 11.4%, which increases the risk of misdiagnosing the disease [84]. Across all ecosystems, urban ecosystems are being impacted by environmental, social, and behavioral factors that may contribute to a rise in the incidence of zoonoses [85–88].

3.1 | Growing Need for Protein Sources

The number of inhabitants on the earth is expected to reach 8.5 billion by 2030. Consequently, the demand for animal-based protein is expected to increase by 14% to satisfy the population's needs. The costs of these necessities are reflected in an increased risk of spreading zoonotic diseases.

Several pathogens in animal meat can be transmitted to humans, causing diseases when the meat is treated before consuming, such as when it is not adequately cooked [89]. In other situations, the meat comes from animals not subjected to regular health checks; this is the case with wild animals' food consumption, which is a significant driver of new zoonoses. In unsustainable livestock farming practices, for instance, in intensive breeding, pathogenic agents can be released into the environment, contributing to the spread of diseases among animal breeders and other workers [90, 91]. The transmission of infectious diseases between domestic animals and humans has been widespread, with many diseases, such as smallpox and tuberculosis, now known to affect humans.

3.2 | Increased Deforestation

Habitat alteration, including deforestation, forest fragmentation, and afforestation, alters the composition and interactions between humans, domestic animals, wild animals, and insects as disease vectors [92, 93]. These changes create new opportunities

for pathogen dissemination and emergence. The industrialization of animal products, caused by the increasing demand for animal-based foods, has led to widespread deforestation and species extinction, which are contributing factors to the spread of zoonotic diseases [94].

3.3 | Extensive Usage and Exploitation of Nature

In some countries, wild species are consumed as food, and bushmeat has contributed to the transmission of diseases such as human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), Ebola, monkeypox, and anthrax [95]. Wildlife harvesting, bushmeat consumption, and wildlife trade often lead to the emergence of new zoonoses [96–98]. The recent COVID-19 is thought to have been generated in bats and may spilled over into human populations through pangolin infection as an intermediate host [99]. Most zoonotic pathogens originate in wildlife, and human–wildlife interactions, including hunting and consumption of animal products, are important sources of exposure to zoonoses [100–104].

3.4 | Urbanization and Human Behavior

The global population is predicted to increase by 32% over the next few decades, reaching 2.3 billion between 2011 and 2050, with most of this growth happening in urban zones of less developed nations [105–107]. The urbanization of human societies has influenced consumer demands and dietary habits, among other factors. Animals and humans can come closer together due to extensive urbanization, which can alter disease ecology and threaten livestock [108, 109]. The risk of zoonotic pathogens emerging from wildlife will undoubtedly increase with human activities that increase interaction with wild animals [110, 111]. Globalization and urbanization strongly impact the epidemiology of vector-borne infectious diseases, which are becoming a threat worldwide [112]. Nevertheless, little is known about the epidemiological processes that underlie this phenomenon. Global biodiversity losses caused by urbanization tend to increase human and animal zoonotic infection risks [113–115].

Traditional rural societies understand and value that biodiversity is essential to their livelihoods and health. Although land use practices tend to be destructive and unsustainable, various external factors, such as policies for economic transformation, are responsible for intellectual and societal losses that have existed for centuries [116]. The challenge of mitigating zoonotic disease outbreaks and addressing conservation issues through participatory methods remains significant, as well as ensuring biodiversity remains aligned [117, 118].

It requires an accounting of what shapes the perceptions of societies and influences knowledge, including societal norms, values, beliefs, and customs. When considering biodiversity from the standpoint of complexity and social science in rural, developing countries, it causes a broader range of issues and gaps [119]. As part of the One Health initiative, both biological diversity and human wellbeing will be addressed through a holistic approach that goes beyond a focus on diseases to other ecological factors [120–122]. There needs to be more consideration of environmental complexity in biodiversity research, which is

why studies have focused almost exclusively on the correlation between biodiversity and zoonosis emergence risk [123–125].

3.5 | Travel and Transportation

The number of people traveling for business, tourism, and other reasons unrelated to moving residences has dramatically increased over the last five decades, and the trend is expected to continue. International trade and travel significantly impact the emergence and/or re-emergence of infectious and VBDs [126]. The spread of tropical diseases such as SARS, MERS, and SARS-CoV-2 has proven that not only are travelers at risk of contracting infectious diseases, but they can also spread them [127–129]. It is well known that numerous infectious diseases, like Zika, dengue, and chikungunya, are often considered “travel-related diseases” imported by travelers or spread by infected carriers accidentally introduced on flights from endemic regions [130].

3.6 | The Changing Food Supply Chains

The growing demand for animal and exotic wildlife products has driven the extension and evolution of food supply chains, resulting in new opportunities for transmitting zoonotic pathogens [131, 132]. As global food demand increases dramatically by 2,100, there will undoubtedly be an increase in newly emerging zoonotic outbreaks and their spread rates [133]. A further consequence of meat consumption is the disruption of natural food chains in natural habitats, resulting in empty landscapes and biodiversity loss [134]. The changing agricultural landscapes have altered the distribution and abundance of disease vectors, leading to an increased risk of VBDs that depend on the specific ecology of the local vectors.

3.7 | Wildlife Zoonotic Management

There is an inherent ethical challenge associated with the management of zoonotic diseases, especially regarding wildlife trade and biodiversity conservation policies, which requires a careful balance among public health, animal welfare, and ecological sustainability to address the issue [135]. The international trade of wildlife, whether legal or illegal, is acknowledged as a key factor contributing to the emergence, and spread of zoonotic diseases because the conditions in which animals are kept and moved in the trade chain can contribute to the spread of pathogens among humans [136]. Meanwhile, it is also critical to consider the economic and social consequences of severely restricting this trade, especially in communities that depend on wildlife resources. This could have unintended consequences, such as increased poaching, which would harm the economy and society [137]. In addition, strict approaches taken to conserve biodiversity may lead local communities to react negatively, and this is especially true when these policies are designed and implemented without the active participation of local stakeholders to avoid such a reaction. The ethical framework that governs zoonotic disease management must take into account not just how to reduce the risk of disease transmission but also how to incorporate principles of environmental justice, Indigenous communities’ rights to sustainable resource use, and international obligations to

protect natural ecosystems into the policy, based on a humanistic perspective [138, 139]. Considering this, it is essential to keep in mind when making decisions concerning wildlife quarantines, trade restrictions, and conservation programs, as inappropriate policies can disrupt ecosystems' balance and even pose a greater risk to human and wildlife interactions. Therefore, if healthcare professionals, biologists, policymakers, and local communities work in coordination to develop solutions that are not only effective in reducing the risk of zoonotic diseases but also protect animal welfare, environmental sustainability, and human rights at the same time, they can also be developed in a multisectoral manner. In order to manage zoonotic diseases ethically, it is important to strike a balance between preventing outbreaks of disease and protecting biodiversity while ensuring economic, social, and environmental benefits for all stakeholder groups and individuals [140–142].

3.8 | Global Warming

The WHO declared global warming and climate change as the most significant threats. Climate changes have altered environmental conditions and increased the risk of zoonotic emergencies, including malaria, cholera, and dengue fever diseases [143, 144]. The effects of climate change can also be seen in the movement of humans and livestock from dry, hot regions to new areas [145, 146], often accompanied by the redistribution of insects and animals. It is well documented how changes in climate and ecosystems, interactions among animals and humans with pathogen-carrying insects, and the spread of zoonoses are all epidemiologically linked [147, 148].

Several studies have suggested climate change may contribute to zoonotic disease outbreaks [149, 150]. A changing climate is expected to affect and influence the incidence of infectious diseases, particularly VBDs, which are influenced by weather and seasonality [151, 152]. Temperature factors are crucial in determining the development and survival of vectors and pathogens in vectors [153]. Changes in the weather could facilitate or aggravate the spread of the disease. According to historical analyses, other factors have been more influential on the planet than climate change. Climate change can affect disease incidence accurately only if there are data to support the projections and because VBDs have complex transmission systems [154–156]. There can be no overstatement of the importance of an integrated framework for climate change, ecosystems, economies, and societies (Figure 2).

4 | Global Health Governance

Global health governance is a set of institutions, policies, and approaches that are implemented on a global level to promote public health and respond to health crises [157]. In addition, this governance is made possible by international cooperation and coordination among different countries and international organizations, which enable them to manage and control global diseases and promote the health of societies at the global level [158–161]. It is important to point out that the concept of global health governance encompasses institutions such as the WHO,

the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), and NGOs that work in concert to promote global health worldwide.

Pandemic diseases spread widely globally and can kill millions of people before disappearing in response to global health surveillance [162, 163]. Due to their specific characteristics, such as high transmissibility and lack of collective immunity, these diseases can be a source of global crises. Global health governance plays a critical role in preventing and treating these diseases, taking various measures to reduce their risks and impacts [164, 165]. Global health governance is one of the most critical tasks that aims to ensure that pandemic diseases do not spread around the globe by developing and implementing international protocols, standards, and guidelines [166]. WHO, as the main body in this field, sets guidelines and protocols for member countries so that in the event of a health crisis, different countries can act in a coordinated and effective manner [167]. These protocols include early detection methods, crisis management, and disease outbreak control strategies.

Global health governance also helps to strengthen health infrastructure in different countries. This includes funding to improve healthcare systems, train the workforce, and upgrade medical equipment [168–170]. Especially in developing countries with poor health infrastructure, these measures can play an important role in dealing with pandemic diseases. Improving health infrastructure allows countries to address health crises more effectively and provide health services to needy populations [171–173].

It is necessary to continue to research and develop in the field of science and technology in order to prevent pandemic diseases. A particular aspect of global health governance is its involvement in funding and supporting scientific research [174]. It is also possible to perform investigative research on innovative prevention methods and the development of new vaccines and treatments in addition to the development of vaccines and new treatments. In order to accelerate the discovery of effective treatments and boost the speed of the research process, it is important to form scientific cooperation between scientists from around the world. It is likely to result in increased efficiency and speed of the research process. As more funding and research resources are allocated to the area of pandemic disease research, researchers will be able to design more practical and scientific solutions to combat these diseases much more quickly and efficiently through the development of more practical and scientific solutions [175, 176].

According to the WHO, zoonotic diseases are infections caused by bacterial, fungal, viral, or parasitic pathogens transmitted from nonhuman species to humans and vice versa. These diseases can spread quickly to humans via direct contact, ingestion of contaminated water or food, or through vector animals, and potentially become pandemics in extreme cases. Global health governance in this field includes monitoring disease outbreaks, formulating control and prevention strategies, and promoting international cooperation to manage zoonotic diseases [6, 177, 178]. This management can include establishing surveillance networks for early detection of zoonotic diseases, holding scientific conferences to exchange information and experiences, and developing prevention and treatment strategies [179].

FIGURE 2 | The image represents zoonotic disease transmission, with an illustration of connectivity among humans, animals, and wildlife. There is a map of the planet in the background, with parts of the world segmented in a range of colors. Overlapping three circles illustrate connectivity: a) one for humans, with a silhouette of a human; b) one for wildlife, with animals including bats, rodents, birds, and primates; and c) one for livestock, with cows, pigs, and chickens. Viral, bacterial, and parasite symbols illustrate disease transmission routes. Arrows illustrate environmental factors such as deforestation and vector-borne disease contributing to pathogen transmission. The picture identifies the zoonotic disease pathway, a consciousness of connectivity between humans, wildlife, and livestock.

Monitoring and predicting the spread of zoonotic diseases requires collecting and analyzing data related to the health status of animals and humans. Global health governance is particularly involved in collecting data from various sources, analyzing outbreak trends, and predicting disease outbreak probabilities [118, 180]. Such monitoring can help identify high-risk areas, assess health needs, and design appropriate strategies to control outbreaks. For example, using advanced technologies such as digital surveillance systems and predictive models can help improve the accuracy and efficiency of zoonotic disease monitoring [181].

Educating and informing communities at risk is one of the other duties of global health governance. These trainings can include information about ways of transmission of diseases, preventive measures, and methods of dealing with diseases. Increasing public awareness can help prevent the spread of zoonotic diseases and reduce their risks [182, 183]. For example, educational programs in local communities, workshops for farmers and ranchers, and public awareness campaigns can help improve knowledge and change health behaviors.

The lack of funding for vaccine research, development, and distribution is one of the biggest challenges in global health governance. This poses a major obstacle to implementing global health policy [184, 185]. Access to resources in many countries can help them deal with health crises, making health services available to all citizens. Health crises pose a significant challenge to countries and international organizations in dealing with such crises effectively. As a result of this lack of coordination, factors

such as the delay in implementing preventive and therapeutic measures can increase disease prevalence and reduce the effectiveness of health measures [186–188].

Developing countries, which have a significantly higher rate of health disparities compared to developed countries, may have trouble managing pandemic diseases due to these disparities. In addition to inequalities in health infrastructure, financial resources, and access to treatments and vaccines, these disparities may also be exacerbated by differences in healthcare services availability [189–191]. Technological advances have contributed to improving the prevention and treatment methods of diseases. In addition to discovering new vaccines, early detection technologies, and novel therapeutics, these advancements have improved health interventions' effectiveness in many ways [192–194].

There are numerous ways in which collaborations can be strengthened, including information networks, international collaborations, and the development of collaborative initiatives to respond effectively to health crises worldwide [195]. For the improvement of these collaborations between different countries and international organizations, information, experiences, and resources can be exchanged [40, 196, 197]. As a result, these organizations are able to develop better coordinated health measures that are more efficient and effective, which, of course, increases their effectiveness. The prevention of diseases and the promotion of global health can both be made possible by increasing public awareness and public education. It is possible to implement a variety of health-related education, awareness, and behavioral change activities within local communities to nurture healthy

habits and reduce the likelihood of developing chronic diseases [198, 199].

Global health governance is essential in preventing pandemics, managing zoonotic diseases, producing and distributing vaccines, and defending against zoonotic diseases [200]. This position entails developing protocols and programs to eradicate pandemics rapidly. It also strengthens health infrastructures, supports scientific research, and monitors vaccine safety and effectiveness [201–203]. By addressing the challenges and opportunities, improving global health governance could greatly help increase global health and respond better to crises [204, 205]. Global health goals can be accomplished, and people's quality of life and public health in the developing world can be improved. This is done by leveraging scientific advances and enhancing international cooperation, as well as promoting public awareness [206, 207].

5 | Discussion

Demonstrating and improving One Health's efficiency remains the greatest challenge. One Health is a transdisciplinary approach built on ecosystems, and it combines current theory and practical skills to create a set of criteria and protocols [208, 209]. These criteria, ranging from the least comprehensive to the most comprehensive interventions, specify the extent of knowledge integration, participation, and systems thinking [210]. Engaging in the process involves negotiating diverse perspectives of the problem and locating relevant knowledge.

Moreover, much work and advancement have strengthened the One Health approach over the past few decades [211]. Still, institutionalization and regular, sustainable operationalization within government institutions remain challenging. Several factors could lead to inefficiencies and ineffective coordination, such as inequalities in the distribution of resources between programs for environmental, animal, and human health, as well as inequalities in education and training across different fields and disciplines [212–214]. One Health approaches to controlling and preventing zoonoses sometimes fail due to insufficient budgeting and coordination. The majority of countries continue to have inadequate information sharing between the human, animal, and environmental health sectors; government officials are not committed to supporting One Health with leadership or funding, especially in developing nations [215–217]. Despite the importance of sustainably institutionalizing and implementing the One Health approach in government institutions, this process faces several challenges that prevent effective coordination and efficient management of zoonotic diseases and other common threats to human, veterinary, and environmental health. One of the main obstacles is the uneven distribution of financial, infrastructure, and human resources among these three areas, which creates inconsistencies in implementation plans and policy prioritization [218, 219]. For example, in many countries, significant investments are mainly focused on the human health sector, whereas the veterinary and environmental sectors face a budget shortage and specialized human resources. This imbalance reduces the capacity of countries to identify and control zoonotic diseases in a timely manner and leads to late and ineffective responses to common health threats.

In addition to the uneven distribution of resources, training gaps and lack of coordination in capacity-building programs across disciplines are also significant obstacles to the effective implementation of One Health [220]. Medical, veterinary, and environmental science professionals in many education systems receive separate training and lack an integrated understanding of interdisciplinary challenges [221, 222]. This leads to weak interdisciplinary collaboration, lack of mutual understanding, and difficulty in joint decision-making. Another key challenge is the lack of effective coordination structures within governments, which leads to fragmentation of tasks across different organizations and reduces the effectiveness of joint policymaking. Some countries have addressed this problem by establishing inter-sectoral institutions and joint committees among health, agriculture, and environmental ministries. These centers have strengthened the implementation of the One Health approach at the national level by holding regular meetings, developing standard protocols, and allocating appropriate resources among different sectors [223]. In addition, using new technologies and advanced information systems can play an important role in promoting coordination among different sectors. The development of digital platforms for sharing health and epidemiological data among medical, veterinary, and environmental institutions can help to identify common threats more quickly and respond to emerging diseases promptly [224, 225].

Zoonotic disease prevention and control measures have competing priorities; diagnostic laboratory capacity to identify causal agents is limited; and there is either no legislation or very little legislation that implements the One Health approach, primarily through public–private partnerships (PPPs) [226–228]. Many universities worldwide do not offer One Health courses in human medicine, veterinary medicine, and other disciplines. Aside from that, the primary obstacles to One Health are the various zoonotic diseases that are emerging or have returned, the increased interactions between humans and animals and their environments due to the exponential growth of livestock and human populations, the fast urbanization and farming systems, the close interactions between domestic animals and wildlife that can lead to forest invasion (which in turn can cause habitat disruption and ecosystem change), the globalization of trade in animals and animal products, antimicrobial resistance, and climate change [229–233]. To overcome the obstacles to the effective implementation of the One Health approach at the global level, it is necessary to carry out fundamental reforms in academic education systems to include this approach as part of the curriculum in medical, veterinary, public health, environmental, and other related fields [234]. In this regard, universities and higher education institutions can strengthen the knowledge and skills necessary for interdisciplinary collaboration by developing interdisciplinary courses, holding joint training workshops, and establishing scientific exchange programs between students and professors of different disciplines [235, 236].

The management of zoonotic diseases, public health, and ecosystems can be adversely affected by the rise of antibiotic resistance, which is one of the key challenges in the implementation of One Health strategies. The problem of antibiotic resistance, which poses a serious threat to global health, has been caused by the overuse and inappropriate use of antibiotics in human, veterinary, and agricultural medicine [237, 238]. This has resulted in the

FIGURE 3 | This diagram shows the four key drivers behind emerging zoonoses. a) illustrates that rapid deforestation is primarily driven by habitat loss, which is portrayed as a tree being chopped down. b) showing how climate change affects disease dynamics. c) represents wildlife contact and biodiversity, crucial to zoonotic transmission, and d) displays human encroachment into habitats, with residential buildings and housing. It can be noticed that a combination of environmental and social factors drives zoonotic diseases.

emergence and spread of antibiotic-resistant bacteria in these environments. As a result, One Health is more challenging to implement, as it makes it more difficult to control infectious diseases in humans and animals due to the decline in the effectiveness of treatments for these diseases. This challenge will be addressed by implementing an integrated strategy in order to reduce the unnecessary use of antibiotics in human and veterinary medicine as part of an integrated approach to address this challenge [239, 240]. For example, there are many countries around the world that have banned the use of antibiotics in livestock and are adopting alternatives to antibiotics, such as probiotics and vaccines. Moreover, by establishing global surveillance systems for antibiotic consumption and the spread of resistance genes, it is possible to reduce the threat of resistance genes spreading across the globe [241, 242].

One of the newest and most promising methods that can help combat antimicrobial resistance is nanotechnology, which can provide a solution of greater effectiveness than traditional antibiotics when it comes to the development of novel antimicrobial drugs, drug delivery systems that are targeted, and alternative treatments for antibiotic resistance [221, 243]. Various metal nanoparticles, such as silver, gold, copper, and zinc oxide, have

a strong ability to fight pathogens [244–246]. In addition, they are capable of exerting practical antimicrobial effects by causing cell wall damage in pathogens, generating reactive oxygen species, and inhibiting key metabolic pathways [247]. Nanoparticles contain numerous properties that are not present in conventional antibiotics, which allows them to circumvent drug resistance and effectively attack a wide range of drug-resistant pathogens. Furthermore, nanodrug delivery systems such as nanocapsules, nanoliposomes, and nanomicelles have the potential to deliver antibiotics to the site of infection in a targeted way, which reduces the amount of drug that the patient needs to take and the side effects associated with the drug [248–250].

Climate change also directly affects the spread of zoonotic diseases, further complicating the implementation of One Health [9]. Rising temperatures, changes in rainfall patterns, and melting polar ice caps are expanding the habitats of disease vectors such as malaria and dengue fever mosquitoes, increasing the risk of new diseases [251]. In addition, climate change is leading to a decline in biodiversity and the destruction of wildlife habitats, bringing animals closer to urban areas and increasing their contact with humans and domestic animals [252, 253]. To mitigate these impacts, policies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions,

FIGURE 4 | As shown in the figure, pandemic responses evolved, highlighting the importance of public health and biodiversity conservation. It also highlights the importance of vaccinations and digital surveillance in controlling diseases. The results of AI-powered diagnostics, combined with one health integration, will shape public health outcomes by showing how disease, technology, and environment are interrelated.

protect forests, and control land use must be considered part of One Health’s strategies. In this regard, developing sustainable agriculture, reducing dependence on fossil fuels, and investing in renewable energy can effectively reduce the effects of climate change on human and animal health [254, 255] (Figure 3).

Public–private partnerships (PPPs) are a key approach to improving global health governance and the effective implementation of One Health solutions [256]. They can be used as a sustainable mechanism for financing, knowledge exchange, and technical and operational capacity building. In the context of pandemic prevention and zoonotic disease management, PPPs can effectively develop and deploy new technologies, establish integrated surveillance and monitoring networks, and improve public health and veterinary infrastructure [257, 258]. For example, collaboration among government agencies, pharmaceutical companies, and research institutions can lead to developing new vaccines and producing more effective drugs to control EIDs. In crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic, PPPs have played an important role in accelerating the research process, vaccine production, and equitable distribution globally.

In addition, PPPs can help improve supply chain management in the health sector. Providing medical equipment, medicines, and vaccines in emergencies often faces resource shortages, uneven distribution, and logistical constraints [259, 260]. In this regard, cooperation among governments, private companies, and international organizations can help create sustainable and efficient supply chains so that essential equipment and medicines

can be sent to affected areas more quickly and effectively [261, 262]. PPPs can also significantly train and improve human resources capacity in human health, veterinary medicine, and the environment. Private companies active in digital technologies and big data can develop smart systems for monitoring zoonotic diseases and digital platforms for sharing health data in collaboration with universities and government agencies [263, 264]. This will help identify pathogens more quickly, better predict disease outbreaks, and provide more targeted responses in times of crisis.

Multilevel integrated activities are needed at grassroots, national, regional, and global levels. It is important to operationalize One Health, and the described lines of work must be implemented through collaboration and intersectional dialog. In order to accomplish One Health objectives, researchers need to cooperate extensively with each other through effective studies on emerging pathogens, mechanisms of disease spillover, and monitoring of the risks associated with the prevention and control of zoonotic and/or infectious diseases [265, 266]. Through strong intersectional collaboration among human health, veterinary health, wildlife, and the environment, regular joint surveillance capabilities can be enhanced, understanding of zoonotic disease emergencies can be better understood, and health measures can be effectively implemented [267]. Institutions and organizations committed to One Health should integrate it into their regular plans and/or activities. Globally, countries must promote the integration of One Health principles into academic curricula and research. Additionally, diagnostic laboratories

FIGURE 5 | This diagram illustrates a “Predicted Health Government” a) at its center for a future or technology-dependent healthcare governance model. Surrounding it, four technological and medical breakthroughs feature prominently: b) AI-guided personalized therapy, with a molecule of DNA and an AI chip; c) nanomedicine, with a nanobot-shaped capsule; and d) vaccine therapy, with a molecular depiction and a syringe. There may be a temple-shaped entity representing regulating frameworks and government intervention, and a heart-shaped sign representing concern for care and tracking of one’s wellbeing. Together, these entities form a model of overall and predictive care through state-of-the-art technology for personalized, effective, and proactive care and management of one’s wellbeing.

need to be expanded, and government leadership needs to be advised or made aware of One Health’s goals. Identifying legal principles and institutional dynamics of relevant sectors beyond their sector-specific legislation is essential for developing legal solutions for implementing the One Health approach [268, 269].

There are several reasons why International Health Regulations (IHR) play such a vital role in the response to a novel outbreak after it takes place [270–272]. In addition to focusing on the prevention of naturally occurring zoonoses, which are estimated to cause up to 75% of all new human diseases, a new instrument could focus on the prevention of naturally occurring zoonoses [273]. Animals and humans should be separated as much as possible, for example, by managing land and reforestation and by regulating trade and markets in wild animals to prevent spillovers between animals and humans [274, 275]. To identify the places where spillovers are likely to occur, researchers have already developed prescriptive models to predict them.

SARS-CoV-2’s ability to cause health, economic, social, and humanitarian crises provides compelling justification for the need for a new international agreement on pandemic prevention and preparedness, given its potential to cause a range of health, economic, and social crises [276–279]. By working together, empowering the WHO to fund it properly, and strengthening the domestic health systems, we can significantly reduce the likelihood of novel outbreaks in the future and strengthen the response to future outbreaks [280, 281] (Figure 4).

A disproportionate number of hospitalizations and deaths were reported as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, and a significant disparity in access to essential medical countermeasures was reported [282–285]. These disparities included racial, ethnic, and sex differences, disabilities, and socioeconomic status [286–288]. In global markets for diagnostics, personal protective equipment, therapeutics, and vaccines, countries with high incomes dominate the market [289, 290]. The WHO and partners have developed the Access to COVID-19 Tools Accelerator as a means

FIGURE 6 | This diagram illustrates health governance at the international and national levels. The central circle displays global health organizations like the World Health Organization (WHO). In addition, there is a ring of regional alliances and surveillance systems. The outer ring comprises research institutions, national health systems, and community-based response teams.

of accelerating the development, production, and equitable distribution of COVID-19 tests, treatments, and vaccines in order to combat the disease [291–293].

To improve global health governance in the future, as well as to prevent pandemics, it is essential that countries and international organizations work together closely to achieve these goals. In one of the key proposals, it is proposed to create a global early warning and response system for health threats in order to increase the ability to detect and predict infectious diseases using advanced technologies, such as data mining and artificial intelligence, with the goal of improving the ability to detect and respond to viral outbreaks. Additionally, local communities need to be trained and empowered in order to be able to perform better in times of crisis and design effective strategies to deal with pandemics with the help of past experiences so that they can respond to this situation in an effective manner. Further, strengthening the health infrastructure of developing countries and providing enough financial and technical resources from developed countries can help reduce health inequalities between countries on a global scale. Lastly, by creating a global network of researchers and experts in the field of public health with the ability to exchange information and experiences on a continuous basis, this will help prevent and control future pandemics as well as improve the performance of global health systems by promoting continuous information exchange (Figures 5 and 6).

6 | Conclusions

In conclusion, effective pandemic prevention requires a comprehensive approach that integrates robust global health governance, international collaboration, and proactive surveillance systems. The current paradigms highlight the importance of coordinated efforts among national governments, global organizations, and stakeholders to ensure rapid response capabilities, equitable access to resources, and the development of resilient healthcare infrastructures. Strengthening early detection techniques, investing in research and innovation, and fostering transparency and accountability across borders are essential to mitigating future pandemic risks and ensuring global health security.

Author Contributions

Hassan Borji, Cinzia Santucci, and Abbas Rahdar: conceptualization. **Soheil Sadr and Shakiba Nazemian:** software. **Hassan Borji, Cinzia Santucci, Shakiba Nazemian, and Soheil Sadr:** validation. **Cinzia Santucci, Soheil Sadr, Narges Lotfalizadeh, Negin Esfandiari, Helia Sepahvand, and Sadanand Pandey:** investigation. **Cinzia Santucci, Soheil Sadr, Narges Lotfalizadeh, Negin Esfandiari, Helia Sepahvand, and Sadanand Pandey:** data curation. **Soheil Sadr:** writing – original draft preparation. **Cinzia Santucci, Soheil Sadr, Narges Lotfalizadeh, Negin Esfandiari, Helia Sepahvand,**

and **Sadanand Pandey**: writing – review and editing. **Abbas Rahdar, Hassan Borji, and Cinzia Santucci**: visualization. **Abbas Rahdar, Hassan Borji, and Cinzia Santucci**: supervision. **Abbas Rahdar, Hassan Borji, and Cinzia Santucci**: project administration. **Cinzia Santucci**: funding acquisition. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Ethics Statement

Not applicable.

Consent

The authors have nothing to report.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article.

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